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2 *Idiomarina aquatica* sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium isolated from Spanish

3 salterns

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5 María José León¹, Fernando Martínez-Checa², Antonio Ventosa¹ and Cristina Sánchez-

6 Porro¹

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8 ¹Department of Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of

9 Sevilla, 41012 Sevilla, Spain

10 ²Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Granada, 18071

11 Granada, Spain

12

13 Correspondence:

14 Cristina Sánchez-Porro (sanpor@us.es)

15 Antonio Ventosa (ventosa@us.es)

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17 **Running title:** *Idiomarina aquatica* sp. nov.

18 **Subject category:** New taxa-Proteobacteria

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20 The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number for the 16S rRNA gene sequence of

21 strain SN-14^T is HF954116.

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24 Four bacterial strains, SN-14^T, SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B, were isolated from water
25 of ponds of two salterns located in Huelva (Spain). They were Gram-staining-
26 negative, aerobic and slightly curved rods. Phylogenetic analysis based on 16S
27 rRNA gene sequences indicate that the four strains belong to the genus *Idiomarina*,
28 being the most closely related species *Idiomarina fontislapidosi* F23^T (98.4-98.0 %
29 sequence similarity), *Idiomarina seosinensis* CL-SP19^T (98.3-98.0 %), *Idiomarina*
30 *piscisalsi* TPS4-2^T (97.9-97.4 %), *Idiomarina baltica* OS145^T (97.5-97.4 %) and
31 *Idiomarina zobellii* KMM 231^T (97.6-97.0 %). The similarity with the type species
32 of the genus, *Idiomarina abyssalis* KMM 227^T was 97.2-96.7 %. The novel strains
33 exhibited optimal growth at 5-10 % (w/v) total salts, pH 7 and at 37 °C. The major
34 fatty acids of strain SN-14^T were iso-C_{15:0} (30.4 %), iso-C_{17:0} (10.7 %), C_{18:1}
35 *ω*7c/C_{18:1} *ω*6c (7.3 %), C_{16:0} (7.1 %) and iso-C_{17:1} *ω*9c/C_{16:0} 10 methyl (7.0 %). The
36 DNA G+C content range was 47.6 to 50.8 mol%. The level of DNA-DNA
37 relatedness between strain SN-14^T and *I. fontislapidosi* F23^T was 13 %, while those
38 between strain SN-14^T and the other four new isolates were between 77 and 99 %.
39 These data demonstrated that the four isolates constitute a new species of the
40 genus *Idiomarina*. Based on the phylogenetic, genotypic, phenotypic and
41 chemotaxonomic data, the four strains represent a novel species of the genus
42 *Idiomarina*, for which the name *Idiomarina aquatica* sp. nov. is proposed. The type
43 strain is SN-14^T (= CCM 8471^T = CECT 8360^T = LMG 27613^T).

45 The genus *Idiomarina* was first proposed by Ivanova *et al.* (2000) and the genus
46 *Pseudidiomarina* was later established by Jean *et al.* (2006). Both genera belong to the
47 family *Idiomarinaceae*, within the order *Alteromonadales*, class *Gammaproteobacteria*
48 in the phylum *Proteobacteria*. In 2009 Taborda *et al.* proposed that the species
49 classified in the genus *Pseudidiomarina* should be transferred to the genus *Idiomarina*,
50 due to the inability to distinguish both genera from each other using the phenotypic or
51 chemotaxonomic characteristics examined. At the time of writing the genus *Idiomarina*
52 comprises 24 species with validly published names (Parte, 2014). Most of these species
53 were isolated from seawater samples and sea salt evaporation ponds. The species of the
54 genus *Idiomarina* stain Gram-negative, are motile rods, colonies are non-pigmented or
55 are slightly yellowish-coloured; NaCl is required for growth, showing a range between
56 0.5 and 25 % (w/v) NaCl and an optimum growth in media containing from 1 to 10 %
57 NaCl. They are strictly aerobic, catalase and oxidase positive. Ubiquinone 8 is the major
58 respiratory quinone. The DNA G+C content ranges from 45 to 54 mol% (Taborda *et al.*,
59 2009).

60 In this study, we describe the isolation and taxonomic characterization of four novel
61 moderately halophilic bacteria from two salterns located in Huelva (Spain) and the data
62 suggest that they constitute a novel species of the genus *Idiomarina*. The
63 characterization of these strains was achieved by following a polyphasic approach,
64 including conventional phenotypic features, chemotaxonomic data (polar lipid, fatty
65 acid and quinone composition) and molecular analysis (16S rRNA gene sequence
66 similarity and DNA-DNA hybridization).

67 Strains SN-14^T and SN-4 were isolated from a water pond of Isla Cristina saltern and
68 strains M6-46 and M6-58B were isolated from water of a pond of Aragonesas saltern,
69 both located in Huelva, in Southwest Spain. The isolation medium was modified from

70 HM medium, previously described by Ventosa *et al.* (1982) and contained (g l⁻¹): NaCl,
71 117; MgCl₂.6H₂O, 19.5; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 30.5; CaCl₂, 0.5; KCl, 3; NaHCO₃, 0.1; NaBr,
72 0.35; yeast extract, 0.05, solidified with 1.8 % agar (BD). The pH of this medium was
73 adjusted to pH 7,5 with 1 M KOH. The strains were isolated by plating 0.1 ml of the
74 water samples on this medium after incubation under aerobic conditions at 37 °C. The
75 strains were subsequently purified three times by plating on the same medium. The
76 strains were routinely grown in SW 7.5 % medium at 37 °C. The composition of this
77 medium was the following: (g l⁻¹): NaCl, 58.5; MgCl₂.6H₂O, 9.75; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 15.25;
78 CaCl₂, 0.25; KCl, 1.5; NaHCO₃, 0.05; NaBr, 0.175 and yeast extract, 5. The pH of this
79 medium was adjusted to 7.5. The strains were maintained on SW 7.5 % medium and at
80 -80 °C supplemented with 30 % (v/v) glycerol. The type strains *I. fontislapidosi* F23^T, *I.*
81 *abyssalis* CIP 107408^T, *I. baltica* DSM 15154^T, *I. piscisalsi* NBRC 108617^T, *I.*
82 *seosinensis* CIP 108665^T and *I. zobellii* DSM 15924^T were used as reference strains for
83 comparison in our study.

84 Cell morphology and motility were examined by phase-contrast microscopy (Olympus
85 CX41) from exponentially growing cultures. Growth range and optimal were
86 determined at different NaCl concentrations (0.5, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 %, w/v) on
87 SW medium at pH 7.5. To determine the optimal and range of temperature and pH for
88 growth of strains, broth cultures were incubated at temperatures of 5-45 °C at intervals
89 of 5 °C and from 35 to 40 °C in increments of 1 °C and at pH 4-10.5 at intervals of 0.5
90 pH units. Growth was determined by monitoring the optical density at 600 nm using a
91 spectrophotometer. Catalase activity was determined by bubble production in 3 % (v/v)
92 H₂O₂ solution. Oxidase activity was examined with 1 % (v/v) tetramethyl-p-
93 phenylenediamine (Kovacs, 1956). Growth under anaerobic conditions was determined
94 by incubation in an anaerobic jar using Anaerogen (Oxoid) to generate anaerobic

95 atmosphere and an anaerobic indicator (Oxoid) in SW 7.5 % solid medium. Hydrolysis
96 of casein, DNA, gelatin, starch, Tween 80 and aesculin, nitrate and nitrite reduction,
97 Simmons' citrate, selenite reduction, Voges-Proskauer and methyl red tests, oxidation-
98 fermentation from carbohydrates, production of indole and phosphatase, urease and
99 phenylalanine deaminase activities were determined as described by Cowan & Steel
100 (1977) with the addition of 7.5 % total salts to the medium (Ventosa *et al.*, 1982;
101 Quesada *et al.*, 1984). H₂S production was tested in SW 7.5 % medium supplemented
102 with 0.05 % (w/v) sodium thiosulfate; with a paper strip impregnated with lead-acetate
103 placed in the neck of the tube (Clarke, 1953). Acid production from carbohydrates was
104 determined using a phenol red base supplemented with 1 % carbohydrate and SW 7.5 %
105 medium. For determination of the range of substrates used as carbon and energy sources
106 or as carbon, nitrogen and energy sources, the classical medium of Koser (1923) as
107 modified by Ventosa *et al.* (1982) was used. This medium contained (l⁻¹): 75 g NaCl, 2
108 g KCl, 0.2 g MgSO₄·7H₂O, 1 g KNO₃, 1 g (NH₄)₂HPO₄, 0.5 g KH₂PO₄ and 0.05 g yeast
109 extract (BD). Substrates were added as filter-sterilized solutions to give a final
110 concentration of 1 g l⁻¹, except for carbohydrates, which were used at 2 g l⁻¹. When the
111 substrate was an amino acid, it was tested as carbon, nitrogen and energy source, and
112 the basal medium was therefore prepared without KNO₃ and (NH₄)₂HPO₄.

113 Cells of the new isolates were motile, slightly curved rods, stained Gram-negative and
114 were strictly aerobic. They were moderately halophilic, growing at 3-15 % (w/v) NaCl,
115 with optimal growth at 7.5 % (w/v) NaCl; they were not able to grow in the absence of
116 NaCl. The temperature range for growth was 5 to 40 °C, with optimal growth at 37 °C.
117 The pH range for growth was 5-10 and the optimal growth was at pH 7.0. Other
118 morphological, physiological, biochemical and nutritional characteristics of strains SN-
119 14^T, SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B are given in the species description and Table 1.

120 The genomic DNA of the four strains was isolated and purified using the method
121 described by Marmur (1961). The 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR with the
122 forward primer 16F27 and the reverse primer 16R1488 (Márquez et al., 2008). Direct
123 sequence determination of the PCR-amplified DNA was carried out using an automatic
124 DNA sequencer (ABI 3139XL, Applied Biosystems). The 16S rRNA gene sequence
125 analysis was performed with the ARB software package (Ludwig *et al.*, 2004). The 16S
126 rRNA gene sequence was aligned with the published sequences from closely related
127 bacteria and the alignment was confirmed and checked against both primary and
128 secondary structures of the 16S rRNA molecule using the alignment tool of the ARB
129 software package. Phylogenetic trees were constructed using three different methods:
130 maximum-parsimony (Fitch, 1971), neighbour-joining (Saitou & Nei, 1987) and
131 maximum-likelihood (Felsenstein, 1981) algorithms integrated in the ARB software for
132 phylogenetic inference. Bootstrap analysis was based on 1000 resamplings (Felsenstein,
133 1985). The 16S rRNA gene sequences used for phylogenetic comparisons were
134 obtained from the GenBank database and their strain designations and accession
135 numbers are shown in Fig. 1.

136 The almost-complete 16S rRNA gene sequence of strains SN-14^T (1460 bp), SN-4
137 (1463 bp), M6-46 (1506 bp) and M6-58B (1477 bp) was obtained and used for initial
138 BLAST searches in GenBank and for phylogenetic analysis. The identification of
139 phylogenetic neighbours and the calculation of pairwise 16S rRNA gene sequence
140 similarities were achieved using the EzTaxon-e server ([http://www.eztaxon-
141 e.ezcloud.net](http://www.eztaxon-e.ezcloud.net)) (Kim *et al.*, 2012). The 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis showed that
142 strains SN-14^T, SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B were members of the genus *Idiomarina*.
143 Their closest relatives were *Idiomarina fontislapidosi* F23^T (98.4-98.0 % sequence
144 similarities), *Idiomarina seosinensis* CL-SP19^T (98.3-98.0 % sequence similarities),

145 *Idiomarina piscisalsi* TPS4-2^T (97.9-97.4 % sequence similarities), *Idiomarina baltica*
146 OS145^T (97.5-97.4 % sequence similarities), and *Idiomarina zobellii* KMM 231^T (97.6-
147 97.0 % sequence similarities). On the other hand, the 16S rRNA gene sequence
148 similarity with the type species of the genus, *Idiomarina abyssalis* KMM 227^T was
149 97.2-96.7 %. Phylogenetic analysis using the maximum-parsimony algorithm revealed
150 that the four strains formed a separate lineage within the genus *Idiomarina*. The
151 phylogenetic position of these strains was also confirmed by trees generated using the
152 neighbour-joining and maximum-likelihood algorithms (Fig. 1). The four strains were
153 included within the rRNA group 1 of the genus *Idiomarina* (Taborda *et al.*, 2009).

154 The G+C content of the genomic DNA was determined from the midpoint value (T_m) of
155 the thermal denaturation profile (Marmur & Doty, 1962) by using the equation of Owen
156 & Hill (1979). The DNA G+C content of strains SN-14^T, SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B
157 was estimated to be 49.4, 47.6, 48.6, and 50.8 mol%, respectively. These values are
158 within the DNA G+C range reported for the genus *Idiomarina* (45 to 54 mol%)
159 (Taborda *et al.*, 2009). DNA–DNA hybridization studies were performed by the
160 competition procedure of the membrane method (Johnson, 1994), described in detail by
161 Arahal *et al.* (2001a, 2001b). The hybridization temperature used was 49.6 °C, which is
162 within the limit of validity for the filter method (De Ley & Tijtgat, 1970), and the
163 percentage of hybridization was calculated according to Johnson (1994). The
164 experiments were carried out in triplicate. DNA–DNA hybridization between strain SN-
165 14^T and SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B was 99, 83 and 77 %, respectively, indicating that
166 the four strains are members of the same species. However, the DNA–DNA
167 hybridization between strain SN-14^T and *I. fontislapidosi* F23^T, *I. seosinensis* CIP
168 108665^T, *I. piscisalsi* NBRC 108617^T, *I. baltica* DSM 15154^T, *I. zobellii* DSM 15924^T
169 and *I. abyssalis* CIP 107408^T was 13, 7, 12, 6, 15 and 17 %, respectively. These levels

170 of DNA–DNA hybridization with respect to the type strains of the phylogenetically
171 most closely related species are significantly lower than the 70 % threshold value
172 recommended for the delineation of new species (Stackebrandt & Goebel, 1994;
173 Stackebrandt *et al.*, 2002).

174 For the analysis of the fatty acids, the cells of strain SN-14^T and the type strain of the
175 most closely related species were grown on marine agar (BD), at 28 °C obtained in the
176 late-exponential growth phase. The whole-cell composition of fatty acids was
177 determined by GC using the MIDI Microbial Identification System (Sasser, 1990). The
178 fatty acids composition was obtained with a gas chromatograph Agilent 6850 using the
179 database TSBA6 (MIDI, 2008). These analyses were carried out by the CECT culture
180 collection (Spain). Analysis of the respiratory quinones and polar lipids of strain SN-14^T
181 and *I. fontislapidosi* F23^T were carried out by the Identification Service of the DSMZ
182 (Braunschweig, Germany). Cell biomass for these analyses was obtained by growth of
183 the strains on marine agar (BD) at 37 °C.

184 The major fatty acids of strain SN-14^T were iso-C_{15:0} (30.4 %), iso-C_{17:0} (10.7 %), C_{18:1}
185 ω 7c/C_{18:1} ω 6c (7.3 %), C_{16:0} (7.1 %) and iso-C_{17:1} ω 9c/C_{16:0} 10-methyl (7.0 %). The fatty
186 acid composition is similar to those of the related species of *Idiomarina*, except for the
187 presence of summed feature 9: iso-C_{17:1} ω 9c/ C_{16:0} 10-methyl (Table 2). Strain SN-14^T
188 exhibited a polar lipid profile consisting of phosphatidylglycerol,
189 phosphatidylethanolamine, two phospholipids and a phosphoaminoglycolipid (atypical
190 sugar). This profile is similar to those reported for species of the genus *Idiomarina*
191 (Taborda *et al.*, 2009). Ubiquinone 8 was the only respiratory quinone detected in strain
192 SN-14^T in accordance with the lipoquinone determined for the family *Idiomarinaceae*
193 and the species of the genus *Idiomarina* (Taborda *et al.*, 2009).

194 The reported phylogenetic, phenotypic, genotypic and chemotaxonomic data clearly
195 indicate that the four strains constitute a single taxon and they represent a novel species
196 of the genus *Idiomarina*, for which we propose the name *Idiomarina aquatica* sp. nov.

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198 **Description of *Idiomarina aquatica* sp. nov.**

199 *Idiomarina aquatica* (a.qua'ti.ca L. fem. adj. *aquatica*, living or found in the water,
200 aquatic).

201 Cells are Gram-staining-negative, motile, slightly curved rods, with 0.4 x 1.25-2.1 μ m,
202 occurring as single cells. Non-endospore-forming. Colonies are circular, entire, smooth,
203 convex, cream and 1.5-2.5 mm in diameter on SW 7.5 % agar medium after 48 h of
204 incubation at 37 °C. Strictly aerobic. Moderately halophilic, growing at 3-15 % (w/v)
205 NaCl, with optimal growth at 7.5 % (w/v) NaCl. No growth occurs in the absence of
206 NaCl. The temperature range for growth is 5-40 °C, with optimal growth at 37 °C. The
207 pH range for growth is 5-10 and the optimal growth is at pH 7.0. Catalase and oxidase
208 positive. Gelatin, Tween 80, DNA and aesculin are hydrolyzed but casein and starch are
209 not. Nitrate and nitrite are reduced (except strain M6-46). Acid is not produced from D-
210 arabinose, D-fructose, D-glucose, D-galactose, lactose, D-mannose, melezitose,
211 melibiose, raffinose, ribose, sucrose, D-xylose, D-mannitol, sorbitol, xylitol, amygdalin,
212 arbutin, citrulline and inulin. Indole or H₂S are not produced. Methyl red, Voges-
213 Proskauer, Simmons' citrate and phenylalanine deaminase tests are negative. Selenite is
214 reduced. Phosphatase and urease are positive. Propionate is used as sole source of
215 carbon and energy. The following compounds are not utilized as sole source of carbon
216 and energy: D-arabinose, D-cellobiose, fructose, D-galactose, D-glucose, lactose,
217 maltose, D-mannose, D-melezitose, D-melibiose, L-raffinose, ribose, salicin, sucrose,

218 D-trehalose, ethanol, glycerol, *myo*-inositol, D-mannitol, methanol, D-sorbitol, xylitol,
219 benzoate, citrate, formate, hippurate, malate, succinate and tartrate. The following
220 compounds are utilized as sole source of carbon, nitrogen and energy: glutamine, and
221 valine. The following compounds are not utilized as sole source of carbon, nitrogen and
222 energy: L.cysteine and L.methionine. The major cellular fatty acids were iso-C_{15:0}, iso-
223 C_{17:0}, C_{18:1 ω7c}/C_{18:1 ω6c}, C_{16:0} and iso-C_{17:1 ω9c}/C_{16:0 10 methyl}. The respiratory
224 isoprenoid quinone is ubiquinone 8 (Q-8). The polar lipid profile consists of
225 phosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylethanolamine, two phospholipids and a
226 phosphoaminoglycolipid. The DNA G+C content is 47.6-50.8 mol% (Tm).

227 The type strain is SN-14^T (= CCM 8471^T = CECT 8360^T = LMG 27613^T), isolated
228 from the water of a pond of Isla Cristina saltern, Huelva (Spain). The genomic DNA
229 G+C content of the type strain is 49.4 mol% (Tm).

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232 **Acknowledgements**

233 This research was supported by grants from the Spanish Ministry of Science and
234 Innovation (CGL2013-46941-P) and the Junta de Andalucía (P10-CVI-6226). FEDER
235 funds and the Plan Andaluz de Investigación also supported this project. M.J. León was
236 recipient of a post-graduate fellowship from the Junta de Andalucía.

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322

323 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics of *Idiomarina aquatica* sp. nov. (strains SN-14^T,
324 SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B) and related species of the genus *Idiomarina*.
325 Strains: 1, SN-14^T; 2, SN-4; 3, M6-46; 4, M6-58B; 5, *Idiomarina fontislapidosi* F23^T
326 and 6, *Idiomarina abyssalis* KMM 277^T. Data were obtained in this study unless
327 mentioned otherwise. +, Positive, -, negative.

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6
Cell morphology	Curved rods	Curved rods	Curved rods	Curved rods	Slightly curved rods ^a	Rod-shaped ^b
Colony pigmentation	Cream	Cream	Cream	Cream	Cream ^a	Light yellowish ^b
Cell size (µm)	1.25-2.1 x 0.4	0.8-1.7 x 0.4	0.8-1.7 x 0.4	1.25-2.1 x 0.4	3.0-4.0 x 0.75 ^a	1-1.8 x 0.7-0.9 ^b
NaCl range (% w/v)	3.0-15.0	3.0-15.0	3.0-15.0	3.0-15.0	0.5-25.0 ^a	0.6-15.0 ^b
NaCl optimum (% w/v)	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	3.0-5.0 ^a	3.0 ^b
Temperature range (°C)	5-40	5-40	5-40	5-40	4-45 ^a	4-30 ^b
Temperature optimum (°C)	37	37	37	37	32 ^a	20-22 ^b
pH range	5-10	5-10	6-10	6-10	5-10 ^a	5.5-9.5 ^b
pH optimum	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7-8 ^a	7.5-8 ^b
Nitrate reduction	+	+	-	+	-	+
Nitrite reduction	+	+	-	+	-	+

Hydrolysis of casein	-	-	-	-	+	-
Simmons' citrate	-	-	-	-	+	+
H ₂ S production	-	-	-	-	+	-
Utilization of:						
Maltose	-	-	+	-	-	-
Raffinose	-	-	+	-	-	-
Citrate	-	-	+	-	-	-
Fumarate	+	+	+	-	+	+
Hippurate	-	-	-	-	+	-
L-Glutamine	+	+	+	-	+	+
L-Threonine	-	-	+	-	-	-
L-Valine	+	-	-	-	-	-
DNA G+C content (mol%)	49.4	47.6	48.6	50.8	46.0 ^a	50.4 ^b

328

329 ^a Data from Martínez-Cánovas *et al.* (2004); ^b Data from Ivanova *et al.* (2000).

330

331 **Table 2.** Cellular fatty acid composition of strain SN-14^T and closely related species of
 332 the genus *Idiomarina*.

333 Strains: 1, SN-14^T, 2, *Idiomarina fontislapidosi* F23^T; 3, *Idiomarina abyssalis* KMM
 334 277^T. All data were obtained using the same growth conditions (marine agar, 28 °C,
 335 late-exponential growth phase). Data from this study, except for *I. abyssalis*. Values are
 336 percentages of the total cellular fatty acids. Only fatty acids amounting to at least 1.0 %
 337 of the total cellular fatty acids of at least one of the strains are shown. -, Not detected or
 338 < 1.0 %.

Fatty acid	1	2	3^a
C _{10:0} 3-OH	1.5	2.1	-
iso-C _{11:0}	3.5	3.6	-
iso-C _{11:0} 3-OH	4.5	4.2	-
iso-C _{12:0} 3-OH	-	1.1	-
iso-C _{13:0}	-	1.3	1.0
iso-C _{13:0} 3-OH	5.2	5.1	-
C _{14:0}	1.4	-	-
C _{15:1} ω8c	-	-	1.3
iso-C _{15:1} F	2.1	1.6	2.3
iso-C _{15:0}	30.4	32.8	33.7
C _{16:0}	7.1	8.7	6.3

Fatty acid	1	2	3^a
Summed feature 3 [*]	5.4	7.6	7.8
Summed feature 9 [*]	7.0	-	-
iso-C _{17:0}	10.7	9.6	11.9
C _{17:1} ω6c	-	-	1.5
C _{17:1} ω8c	1.3	1.5	-
C _{17:0} cyclo	2.8	1.4	-
C _{17:0}	2.8	2.4	-
Summed feature 8 [*]	7.3	4.2	6.7
C _{18:0}	3.4	2.5	1.8
C _{18:1} ω9c	-	-	1.4

339 *Summed features are groups of two or three fatty acids that could not be
340 separated by GC with the MIDI system. Summed feature 3 comprised C_{16:1} ω7c
341 and/or C_{16:1} ω6c; summed feature 8 comprised C_{18:1} ω7c/ C_{18:1} ω6c; summed
342 feature 9 comprised iso-C_{17:1} ω9c and/or C_{16:0} 10-methyl.

343 ^aData from Ivanova *et al.* (2000).

344

345 **Legend to figure**

346 Fig. 1. Maximum-parsimony phylogenetic tree based on nearly complete 16S rRNA
347 gene sequences showing the relationships between *Idiomarina aquatica* (strains SN-
348 14^T, SN-4, M6-46 and M6-58B), related species of the genus *Idiomarina* and other
349 related genera. Filled circles indicate nodes that were also recovered in neighbor-joining
350 and maximum-likelihood trees based on the same sequences. Numbers at nodes are
351 levels of bootstrap support (percentages) based on analyses of 1000 resampled datasets;
352 only values >70 % are shown. The sequence of *Agarivorans albus* MKT 106^T was used
353 as outgroup. Bar, 0.01 nucleotide changes per position. The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ
354 accession number of each sequence is shown in parenthesis.

